

SCIENCE

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there's
something
science
can do.

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[New study measures national technological trajectories using international patent data:](#)

Professors at the London School of Economics and Political Science have derived measures of national technological trajectories defined as a country's relative rate of innovation. Moving away from domestic patent analysis, the study examines the international patenting activity of 40 countries in the US, UK, France and Germany over 200 years. The analysis shows that Japan came in first, followed by the US and Germany. A nation's innovation output seems to correlate with a triad of initial policy decisions: the scale of R&D intensity, the expertise of the work force, and the depth of its defense-related investments.

[Data governance question in the WHO Pandemic Agreement worries the Global South:](#)

The WHO Pandemic agreement is currently in a deadlock over pathogen genetic data governance in open access databases. While global health leaders advocate for unrestricted data sharing to accelerate vaccine development, countries in the Global South fear that their biological data will be used to the profit of firms in the Global North without guaranteed returns. These countries argue that openness, as was the case during the COVID-19 pandemic, often allows wealthy nations to benefit from shared data without any return to them.

[NASA makes over 100 000 new data files publicly available:](#) Launched in 2025, the [NASA-ISRO synthetic aperture radar](#) (NISAR) satellite uses radar technology instead of typical optical imaging. This ensures consistent, high-resolution mapping of the Earth's surface regardless of weather or light conditions. NISAR also distinguishes itself as the first satellite to employ dual-wavelength radar systematically measuring changes of the Earth's surface with extreme precision. The mission team has openly released over 100 000 new data files available to scientists to help better manage natural resources, prevent natural disaster and study global warming.

[Open science initiative permits accelerated discovery of next generation nonhormonal contraceptives:](#) Gates Foundation is funding a large-scale open access project aimed at accelerating research and development for women's health innovations. For example, by utilizing an entirely open-science based approach, researchers in the US and India have accelerated drug discovery by developing five sperm-specific enzyme probes in less than a year.